

MEDICAL HIGHER EDUCATION IN DEVELOPING UZBEKISTAN: PROBLEMS OF EDUCATION QUALITY AND REFORMS IN MEDICAL INDUSTRY

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the quality of the medical industry in regard to the recent decrees of the republic of Uzbekistan is being analyzed. Also, the effects of the reforms in the laws effecting the medical studies are being considered. As a result of the study, it is found that most of the established new laws are being neglected by the official and the signs of these neglection is visible in the treatment procedure of the population. Hence, we can say that the recent reforms in law will be unsuccessful unless it is applied effectively by the help of authorized organizations.

Keywords: Quality, medical technology, fundamental reforms, authority.

The complexity of the healthcare system is that it is a process directly related to the a responsible activity which is protecting human health and saving life. Of course, the field of medicine is developing very much in the world today. Experiences gained in the fight against various diseases, in carrying out delicate surgical operations aimed at their elimination, are also increasing, and new medical technologies are coming in.

The most important issue of today is the correct use of these achievements, experiences, and existing medical technologies.

At the beginning of his presidency, Shavkat Mirzayoyev, the head of state defined the issue of protecting public health and improving quality medical services as one of the priority tasks. He put on the agenda the need to carry out fundamental reforms in the health care system, especially to implement effective measures to reduce maternal and infant mortality as much as possible.

The situation in Uzbekistan and the existing problems hindering its development were analyzed in depth. It was emphasized that the unsatisfactory performance of the

primary system in the field of health care is the cause of public objections, and that the work being done to eliminate existing problems is ineffective from an economic point of view. Solving these problems is one of the important tasks of today. The contact of the specialized centers with the lower strata of the population was almost cut off. For this reason, it was noted that they do not meet international standards, and internal communications have not been established among the clinics. In fact, for development in all areas, including in the field of medicine, international experiences are as necessary as oxygen in the air.

To ensure social stability, economic development, and peace in our society, the state conducts a strong social policy for people to live a healthy and prosperous life. Taking this into account, great creative work was carried out in Uzbekistan from the initial stages of the Action Strategy to ensure the well-being and quality of life of the population. Today, more than 60 percent of the State budget is directed to the development of the social sector. Special attention is being paid to improving the living conditions of this population, increasing the quality of life, and improving the health care system.

As stated in the Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the Parliament, several decisions and decrees were adopted to improve the health of the population during the year 2018, with the aim of improving the well-being of the population of the country. At the same time, the transfer of some functions of state medical institutions to the private sector of health care, the development of public-private partnership in this field, as well as the improvement of the qualifications of medical personnel in the republic and abroad, and the introduction of the system of accreditation of medical organizations remain relevant. In accordance with the Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 1, 2017 "On measures for the further development of the private sector in the field of health care" No. wide-scale work was carried out aimed at improving the system of registration and licensing, encouraging the increase in the volume and types of services provided.

In 2019-2025, the concept of health care system development in the Republic of Uzbekistan was developed. The main goals of the concept are:

1. To increase life expectancy by improving the prevention and treatment of diseases and conditions that lead to premature death and disability in most cases.
2. Reform the system of financing and organization of health care to ensure equal access to medical care, financial protection of the population and fair distribution of resources.

3. To strengthen the capacity of health management bodies, to increase the role and responsibility of their leaders to fulfill the tasks of the concept and improve the quality of medical care provided to the population of the republic.

With a goal of improving the medical industry, in addition to above mentioned decrees, over 30 decrees have also been signed and ordered to be implemented in the field.

In Uzbekistan, all conditions are being created for the health of children, for their growth and development. The government spares neither attention nor funds in this regard. Even our unborn children are under the care of our state during the fetal period. On December 25, 2017, the President signed the Decision "On the State program for the early detection of congenital and hereditary diseases in children in the period of 2018-2022" is proof of our above opinion.

This is the main goal of the reforms to be implemented by authorities in the country. Ensuring the health of the future generation. Regardless of which field the representative is today, the health of tomorrow's children, the purity of the generation, must be the demand of the times.

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